

Research Article

**DETERMINATION OF PESTICIDE RESIDUES IN SOIL SAMPLES COLLECTED
FROM WURNO IRRIGATION FARM, SOKOTO STATE, NIGERIA**

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Abstract

Pesticide residues of most commonly used classes were analysed in soil samples collected from Wurno irrigation field. All the 17 soil samples analysed were found contaminated with used pesticides (i.e dichlorvos, mevinphos, dimethoate, femitrothion, chlorpyrifos, endosulfan, methylparathion, profenofos, γ HCH, DDT, dieldrin, endrin and drins), and varying degree of contaminants and frequency were found in the top soil. The most widely detected pesticide residue was DDT found in 16 samples with a mean level of 2.22 measuring a total of 24.10% of the detectable residue, the second most detected pesticide residue was chlorpyrifos, having a total of 17.04% of the detectable residue. γ HCH was the third most detectable residue in the sample with a total of 14.77% of the detectable residue. Analysis also showed that the two fallow soil samples have very low levels (< 1%) of the total detectable residues.

Key words: pesticides, residues, organochlorine, organophosphorus, soil.

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Introduction

Intensive agricultural practices often include the use of pesticides to enhance crop yields. However the improvement in yield is sometimes concomitant with the occurrence and persistence of pesticide residues in soil and other environmental matrices (Wares and Whitacre, 2012). Pesticides may reach the soil through direct application to the soil surface, incorporation in the top few inches of soil, or during application to crops (McEwen and Stephenson, 2012). The fate of pesticide in soil environment is influence by the physico-chemical properties of the pesticide, the properties of the soil system (pressure of clay materials, organic matter, pH, climate, biology, and other factors (Singh, 2011). The increased and indiscriminate use of pesticides has caused pollution of soils

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worldwide. Organochlorine pesticide residues, particularly the oxidized form of heptachlor, remain in soils compartment long after their use has been disconnected (Kim and Smith, 2011). Residues of toxaphene, DDT, trifluralin, and hexachlorocyclohexane (lindane) have been detected in soils from cotton fields in South Carolina (Kannan *et al.*, 2013). The DDTs were the main contaminants detected in soil from Banjul and Dakar in West Africa (Manirakiza *et al.* 2013).

The use of pesticides in Nigeria has continued to increase, particularly in large-scale commercial farming enterprises due to increases in acreage and need to intensify agricultural production. In particular, the tremendous growth in cereals production with subsequent increase in their yield has been attributed to the use of herbicides. However, with this increase in pesticide usage in agriculture, better management and control of pesticides application will be required in future because of the residue limit specification as well as the need to safeguard against the potential adverse effects on the local environment and human (Lalah *et al.* 2011; Schulz, 2012). In addition to keeping accurate records of pesticide usage in the farms, it is necessary to monitor the distribution, fate, and effects of pesticide residues within the ecosystem. Monitoring of pesticide residues in agricultural soil, streams, and rivers within catchments and modeling of their fate and toxicity have become useful global approaches of assessing pesticide efficacy and ecological impact on a given area (Krenger, 2008; Liess *et al.* 2009; Batch *et al.* 2010; Muller *et al.* 2011).

There are a large number of pesticides currently in use, with a wide range of physico-chemical properties and belonging to a wide variety of chemical classes. Clearly, the physico-chemical properties of a given pesticide will govern its behaviour in the soil and its biological activity.

Molecular size, ionisability, water solubility, lipophilicity, polarisability and volatility are all key properties, but generally one or two properties have a dominating influence (Bailey and White, 2010; Weber, 2012; Stevenson, 2006; White, 2006).

Adsorption is probably the most important mode of interaction between soil and pesticides and controls the concentration of the latter in the soil - liquid phase. Adsorption processes may vary from complete reversibility to total irreversibility. The extent of adsorption depends on the properties of soil and the compound, which include size, shape, configuration, molecular structure, chemical functions, solubility, polarity, polarizability and charge distribution of interacting species, and the acid-base nature of the pesticide molecule (Bailey and White, 2010; Senesi, 2012; Pignatello and Xing, 2012).

Adsorption may be purely physical, as with van der Waals forces, or chemical in nature, as with electrostatic interactions. Chemical reactions between unaltered pesticides or their metabolites often lead to the formation of stable chemical linkages, resulting in an increase in the persistence of the residue in soil, while causing it to lose its chemical identity (Berry and Boyd, 2011; Calderbank, 2011; Bollag, 2012; Dec and Bollag, 2012). From a toxicological perspective, binding of xenobiotics to humus leads to: (1) a decrease of material available to interact with biota; (2) a reduction in the toxicity of the compound; and (3) immobilising the compound, thereby reducing

its leaching and transport properties (Berry and Boyd, 2011; Calderbank, 2011; Bollag, 2012; Dec and Bollag, 2012).

It is generally acceptable that climatic conditions in the tropics facilitate the breakdown of bioactive compounds, thus eliminating most of the side effects of pesticides. Pesticide monitoring in the environment is therefore necessary for risk assessment and environmental management in Nigeria due to its different climatic conditions when compared with those of temperate countries. Nigeria is at the crossroad of environmentally sustainable agricultural practices characterized by high usage of agrochemicals and development of sound environmental policies for environmental protection. The current rural-to-urban migrations necessitate the use of herbicides as an alternative to manual weed control, particularly in large-scale farming practices. Therefore, pesticide use in Nigeria is expected to continue increasing. High concentration levels of pesticides would therefore present a potential risk to the environment and human health in the Wurno areas and their application must be regulated at the application site in order to avoid unacceptable levels of residues reaching sensitive environmental compartments. The potential contamination of the aquatic environments in Wurno irrigation farm with pesticides, especially herbicides has recently caused concern and has therefore necessitated this study.

Materials and Methods

Description of sample site

Wurno Irrigation farm is located in Wurno Local Government Area of Sokoto state, Nigeria. The total farm areas cover over 1200 hectares (Hamza, 2004). The area is densely populated, rich in agriculture and a major producer of rice, millet, maize, onions, vegetables, etc for the state and neighbouring country. Cattle, sheep, goat, and poultry are also kept. The area is popularly known for the extensive dry season farming which is facilitated by the establishment of a dam. The sampling sites for residue determination were specifically located in the farm irrigation area, where pesticides are extensively used to control weeds and other pests (Fig.1).

Table 1 showing soil sampling stations and GPS Coordinates of each sampled area

Sample code	Soil Dept. (cm)	GPS Coordinate		Other Comments
		X	Y	
SS1	0 – 15	531831	1321230	Cultivated soil
SS2	0 – 15	534103	1321140	Cultivated soil
SS3	0 – 15	535744	1322820	Cultivated soil
SS4	0 – 15	538478	1325810	Cultivated soil
SS5	0 – 15	536795	1326320	Cultivated soil
SS6	0 – 15	539740	1329220	Cultivated soil
SS7	0 – 15	540708	1331620	Cultivated soil
SS8	0 – 15	542980	1332210	Cultivated soil
SS9	0 – 15	543022	1330140	Cultivated soil
SS10	0 – 15	546219	1329640	Cultivated soil
SS11	0 – 15	550300	1330940	Cultivated soil
SS12	0 – 15	550973	1333640	Cultivated soil
SS13	0 – 15	553118	1331030	Cultivated soil
SS14	0 – 15	553539	1328970	Cultivated soil
SS15	0 – 15	556231	1331030	Cultivated soil
SS16	0 – 15	545789	1325980	Fallow soil
SS17	0 – 15	547144	1320800	Fallow soil

Note. X = Latitude, Y = Longitude, SS = Soil Sample

Sampling Method

A 500-gram composite soil sample was collected from the surface (0 - 15 cm deep) with a stainless steel shovel, and stored in a Ziploc bag. The location and description of each sampling site was recorded in details shown in Table 1. A diagram of composite sampling is shown in Figure 2. After sampling, the soil samples are air-dried, sieved to eliminate organic fragment and aggregates, and transferred into clean glass-amber container and stored at ambient temperature prior to analysis

Figure 2 Diagram of composite sampling.

Treatment of Samples

Soil samples were collected in the study areas. Each soil sample was a composite of 10 subsamples collected at each site using random sampling within a grid (Fig 2). A grid was established by identifying the approximate center of a field and dividing the field into 3 rows, 20 paces apart, with 3 core samples taken per row for a total of 10 cores (Mullins *et al.* 2011). Soil was collected from the 0-15 cm layer using a 19" stainless steel shovel. The subsamples were placed into a 16-liter bucket, thoroughly mixed, and sifted through a No.5 (4 mm/0.1575") brass soil sieve (W.S. Tyler™) at the collection site. After each sample was collected, the shovel, bucket, sieve and mixing tool were rinsed before next use. Two of the seventeen samples collected at each site was obtained from an uncultivated field and used as a control. Soil samples were then air dried and sieved through a No.20 (850 μm/0.0335") brass soil sieve (W.S. Tyler™) and refrigerated at about 4°C prior to laboratory analysis.

The method reported by Tahir *et al.* (2009) was followed for the extraction of pesticide residues in soil. 50g of soil sample were taken in a conical flask and then 150ml of a mixture of acetone, hexane (1:1) was added. This was shaken for 1hr with the help of mechanical shaker at a rate of 300 osc/min. The mixture was filtered through a glass wool plug with whatman filter paper No 542 into a separatory funnel. The extract was washed with distilled water (2x100ml). The lower aqueous layer was discarded and a few grams of anhydrous sodium sulphate were added. 20ml of the aliquot was transferred to round bottom flask and evaporated to dryness at 40°C in a rotary evaporator. The contents of the flask were reconstituted in 6ml ethyl acetate and cyclohexane (1:1)

mixture. The sample was again dried and reconstituted in 1ml ethyl acetate and then passed through high flow super cells. 2ml of the sample was applied on Gel Permeation Chromatography (GPC) for further cleanup. After passing through GPC column, the samples were again dried under vacuum and reconstituted in 1ml ethyl acetate for analysis on GC.

Pesticide Standards

All pesticide standards were purchased from Bristol Scientific Co. Nig. A subsidiary of Sigma Aldrich Germany. Stock solutions were prepared using pesticide grade solvents. Spiking solutions for measuring method efficacy (percent recovery) were prepared from stock solutions. Calibration standards in at least three concentrations were also prepared from stock solutions and diluted in hexane. All stock, spiking and calibration standards were transferred to Qorpak™ glass jars after preparation and stored at 4°C. Calibration curves of working standards were used to evaluate the linearity of the gas chromatograph response each day of analysis and pesticide residues were quantified based on these external standards.

Gas Chromatographic Analysis

Soil extracts were analyzed using an Agilent 6890 gas chromatograph equipped with a ⁶³Ni micro-electron capture detector (μECD), capillary column, and Hewlett Packard Chemstation software (GC 2071, Rev.A.06.01). The primary capillary column for separation of pesticides was RTX-5 (Restek, 30 m x 250 μm x 0.25 μm) and confirmation runs were completed using RTX-35 (Restek, 30 m x 250 μm x 0.25 μm). Helium was used as the carrier gas at a constant column flow rate of 1.1 mL/min and the detector makeup gas was nitrogen at a flow rate of 60 mL/min. Samples were injected in the splitless mode with the purge flow to split vent set at 35 mL/min at 1 min and pressure at 15 psi and total flow at 39 mL/min. The injector temperature was either 250°C (RTX-5 injections) or 225°C (RTX-35 injections) and the detector temperature was 350°C. Two different temperature programs were used for the RTX-5 and RTX-35 columns to achieve the separation of pesticides of interest. The temperature program on the RTX-5 capillary column was as follows: 90°C for 0.00 min, 30°C/min to 190°C held for 20 min, 20°C/min to 275°C held for 10 min. For confirmation runs, the temperature program on the RTX-35 column was as follows: 100°C for 2.0 min, 15°C/min to 160°C, 5°C/min to 270°C held for 5 min.

Quantification Limit

The quantification limit (QL), for pesticides reported in this study, was based upon the lowest concentration that could be consistently and/or reliably recovered (> 70%) in our laboratory from fortified samples (Scholtz and Flory 1999). If this percent recovery could not be achieved, the most consistent pesticide recovery was used to establish the quantification limit.

Figure 3: The percentage distribution of pesticide residues in soil samples collected from Wurno irrigation farm.

Discussion

Table 2 shows the pesticide residues in the soil samples collected from Wurno irrigation farm. A total of seventeen soil samples were collected at different locations in the farm area and analysed for the residues of dichlorvos, mevinphos, dimethoate, femitrothin, chlorpyriphos, endosulfan, methylparathion, profenofos, γ HCH, DDT, dieldrin, endrin, and drins.

In soil sample SS1 the residues were in the range of 0.22 - 2.89 μ g/g with the least level found in mevinphos and the maximum level in DDT. In soil sample SS2, the lowest level of residues (0.11 μ g/g) was found in drins and the maximum level of (2.34 μ g/g) was found in DDT. Dimethoate has the lowest level of (0.21 μ g/g) in sample SS3, with the maximum level of (2.13 μ g/g) found in DDT. In soil sample SS4 the minimum level of (0.11 μ g/g) was found in endrin and a maximum level of (2.87 μ g/g) in chlorpyriphos. In SS5 minimum level of (0.23 μ g/g) residue was found in mevinphos, maximum of (2.51 μ g/g) found in DDT. Soil sample SS6 has a minimum level of (0.22 μ g/g) in drins and a maximum level of (2.21 μ g/g) in DDT. Sample SS7 has a minimum level of (0.72 μ g/g) in mevinphos and a maximum level of (1.91 μ g/g) in methylparathion. In soil sample SS8, the minimum level of (0.44 μ g/g) was found in femitrothin and a maximum of (2.98 μ g/g) in DDT. Sample SS9 has a maximum level of (2.66 μ g/g) in DDT and a minimum level of (0.71 μ g/g) in endrin. Sample SS10 has a minimum level of (0.54 μ g/g) in mevinphos and a maximum level of (1.11 μ g/g) in endosulfan. Soil sample SS11 has a minimum concentration of (0.22 μ g/g) in mevinphos and a maximum of (3.79 μ g/g) in DDT. Soil sample SS12 has a minimum concentration of (0.09 μ g/g) found in dieldrin and a maximum concentration of (1.31 μ g/g) in DDT. Sample SS13 has a minimum concentration of (0.47 μ g/g) found in endrins and a maximum concentration of (2.70 μ g/g) found in DDT. Sample SS14 has a minimum

concentration of (0.90 $\mu\text{g/g}$) detected in femitrithin and a maximum of (2.23 $\mu\text{g/g}$) detected in chlorpyrifos. Sample SS15 has a minimum concentration of (0.31 $\mu\text{g/g}$) detected in dieldrin and a maximum concentration of (2.51 $\mu\text{g/g}$) found in DDT. Sample SS16 one of the samples collected at the uncultivated site has a minimum concentration of (0.25 $\mu\text{g/g}$) in endosulfan and a maximum of (1.72 $\mu\text{g/g}$) in DDT. Soil sample SS17 the second sample taken from the fallow site has a minimum concentration of (1.20 $\mu\text{g/g}$) detected in γHCH and a maximum concentration of (1.55 $\mu\text{g/g}$) found in DDT.

Most of the soil samples collected from Wurno irrigation farm was found to be contaminated with pesticide residues at different levels. The most widely detected pesticides was DDT found in 16 of the seventeen samples analysed with mean level of (2.22), covering a total of (24.10%) figure 3; in the detectable residues. Chlorpyrifos was the second most often detected pesticides investigated in 15 samples having the mean concentration of (1.57) giving a total of 17.04%. γHCH was the third most abundant pesticide detected in 15 samples with mean concentration of (1.36) measuring a total of 14.77% in the detectable residues. The mean of Σ -pesticides was found to be (9.21) \pm (3.64) at 95% confidence level in soil samples collected with highest value of (15.93 $\mu\text{g/g}$) in soil sample from SS1 followed by (13.43 $\mu\text{g/g}$) in SS15, (12.83 $\mu\text{g/g}$) in SS3, (12.41 $\mu\text{g/g}$) in SS2, (11.63 $\mu\text{g/g}$) in SS11, (10.91 $\mu\text{g/g}$) in SS4, (10.52 $\mu\text{g/g}$) in SS5, (10.36 $\mu\text{g/g}$) in SS13, while other samples (47%) were found contaminated at residue level less than (10.00 $\mu\text{g/g}$). Presently the pesticides used are mostly synthetic organic compounds. The soil may act as an important sink for persistent organic pollutants including many pesticides used presently or in the past. They are relatively insoluble in water and are retained strongly by the soil. Soil acts as filter buffer and degradation of pollutants with respect to storage of pollutants with the help of soil organic carbon (Burael and Bassmann, 2005). Soil acts as a pathway of pesticide transport to contaminate ground/surface water, plants, food and effects on human via runoff, leaching, transfer of mineral nutrients and pesticides from soil into the plants and animals that constitute the human food chain (Abraham, 2012). Persistent pesticides slowly break down in the soil and lead to contamination which is closely correlated to human activities like industrial discharge, agricultural applications and deforestation which lead to soil erosion (Bhattacharya *et al.*, 2013).

In this study the soil samples analysed were collected from the major agricultural site in Sokoto state. Most of the soil samples collected were contaminated with pesticides. The most widely detected pesticides which are currently or have been used heavily in the past include, DDT (24.10%), Chlorpyrifos (17.04%), γHCH (14.77%), endosulfan (8.25%). This result obtained in Wurno irrigation field is in good agreement with data from similar investigations. Endosulfan an organochlorine (OC) pesticide was reported as pesticides of the particular concern in soils from Queensland irrigation area above the environmental guidelines (0.01 $\mu\text{g/L}$) (Simpson, 2008). The most often detected pesticides in the soil are the OC found in 78 samples out of 103 (Muller, *et al.*, 2010). These findings are in complete agreement with the present findings where OC (endosulfan, DDT, dieldrin, endrin and drins) are encountered. DDT and endosulfan due to their persistency and commonly used features on crops were frequently found when applied in the past in the soils.

Several studies (Singh *et al.*, 2005; Gao *et al.*, 2005) have reported the detection of pesticides in the soil and the most frequent pesticide detected were of OC group which is more persistent and stay in the soil and sediments, decomposed very slowly and may persist for several years as they are insoluble in water and are retained by the soil. DDT (long banned insecticide) was detected in most of soil samples. Baig, (2005) reported DDT in organic soil of Punjab. Most of the DDT applied were found retained on top 5cm layer in sandy loam soil (Hussain *et al.*, 2008; Jabba, *et al.*, 2013).

Tariq *et al.* (2006) studied the hydrophobicity and persistence of pesticides that controlled the accumulation in different soil series of Pakistan. It was observed that less water soluble (<1mg/l) pesticides have the potential to accumulate in soil and aquatic biota, which is in full agreement with present study where most of the pesticides used are insoluble in water so that they persist in the soil without any influence of temperature, humidity and microbial activity on degradation and persistence of commonly used pesticides in sandy loam soils (Tariq *et al.*, 2006). Pesticide that breakdown rapidly are not likely to be detected in groundwater. Some pesticides like OC decompose very slowly and may persist for years and are retained by the soil due to their insolubility in water.

In this study the detection of pesticides in soil from different locations demonstrated the difference in pesticide residues that could be related to the cultivation of crops with different time intervals and pesticide usage like chlorpyrifos in 15 out of 17 samples (present study) while it was detected only in one and eight samples of Bahawalpur and Lodhrum respectively out of twelve soil samples (Anwar, 2009). Pesticides such as endosulfan, DDT, chlorpyrifos, dimethoate appeared widely distributed in soil from different location in Wurno irrigation field. The pesticide retained for a longer period of time in the soil, pass into various parts of plants grown on the contaminated soil. Although the usage of the banned organochlorine pesticides such as endosulfan, dieldrin, DDT, and endrin in the study area was not established during the market survey in the studied area, their presence in the farm soil was assumed to be due to previous application, high residual retention during the slow and gradual phase of dissipation from the soil following previous application, and/or illegal recent usage. Mean concentrations of endrin and dieldrin, which is an epoxide of aldrin, in soil were 0.46 and 0.51, respectively (Table 2). Aldrin in soil is changed by photolysis and microbial action to dieldrin which then degrades very slowly in soil, water, and sediment. Lindane detected at 1.36 levels in the present study may be photolyzed to β -BHC or to tetra- or penta-chlorinated cyclohexanes on exposure to sunlight (Diaz *et al.*, 2009). These chemical changes could influence the concentrations in soil, water, and sediment, with time. Although pesticides are perceived to dissipate faster in the tropics due to adverse environmental factors (Lalah *et al.*, 2011; Wandiga 2011; Diaz *et al.*, 2009; Bereket 2010; Matsumura 2009), other factors such as intensive initial applications, bound residue formation with time and soil cover by grass, preventing loss due to photodegradation, volatilization, and leaching, may have contributed to the persistence of these high residue levels in the soil. Due to their high water solubilities, pesticides such as dichlorvos (water solubility: 242 mg/L), mevinphos (42 mg/L), fenitrothion (33 mg/L), and methylparathion (33,000 mg/L), which are used in the study site, therefore, would pose

a threat to aquatic organisms through runoffs and leaching into water canals and River Lugu during heavy rains.

The high level of Chlorpyrifos (an organophosphate pesticide) observed in this work could be attributed to high initial usage and frequency of application as this substance form a major component of several pesticide formulations. Again the detection of pesticide residues in the two fallow soil samples ie SS16 and SS17 with no history of direct application further goes to confirm the versatility and persistence of these compounds.

Conclusion

Pesticides are applied to protect plants from diseases, weeds and insect damage, and usually come into contact with soil. Undoubtedly, the use of pesticide to control pest in agriculture has greatly improved agricultural yield and improve crop production to cater for the ever increasing population. But the use of agrochemicals to improve yield has also come with the attendant problems of having to cope with the residues, metabolites and degradation products of these chemicals usually left behind in the soil. These residues, metabolites and degradation products once released into the soil can pass to different compartments in the ecosystem posing serious environmental problems.

In this study, it was found that a large variety of insecticides, herbicides, and fungicides are used in the Wurno irrigation farm. There were no complete records of quantities and no information at all on their usage as most of the farmers in this area are uneducated. The concentration levels of individual pesticide residues including dieldrin, DDT, endosulfan, chlorpyrifos and HCH are high. This indicates potential health risks to the local community who depend on agricultural activities mainly for survival. This high level of residues on soil can also spill into the water body during rainfall and their persistence in the soil can also cause leachy into groundwater thus contaminating the ecosystem. It is therefore concluded that to prevent adverse effect on public health it is a must to carry out regular monitoring system of these kinds for the establishment of safety measures.

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